

The impact of school culture on the quality of education in Vietnamese teacher training colleges: a case study in the Red River Delta

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ABSTRACT

School culture is a system of beliefs, values, norms, habits, and traditions developed throughout the school's evolution, recognized and followed by its members, and expressed in both material and spiritual forms. This unique identity shapes each educational institution. The school's culture influences the behavior, attitudes, goals, and outcomes of its students. Based on the intrinsic nature and role of school culture, this study clarifies the correlation between culture and training quality in teacher training colleges in the Red River Delta, Vietnam. Through survey results, observations, and interviews, this research establishes a significant correlation between positive cultural elements and enhanced educational quality indicators, including student achievement, teacher satisfaction, and research productivity. Conversely, negative cultural aspects are found to adversely impact these indicators. The study emphasizes the vital role of school culture in shaping educational experiences and outcomes in Vietnamese teacher training colleges. Based on these findings, the research offers practical recommendations for fostering a positive school culture, thereby contributing to the improvement of teacher training quality in Vietnam.

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1. INTRODUCTION

School culture, encompassing shared values, beliefs, norms, and behaviors, has been widely recognized as a pivotal factor influencing the quality of education. It is often referred to as the "soul" of an educational institution, shaping interactions, communication, and the overall learning environment within schools [1]. Beyond being a physical or organizational framework, school culture reflects the deeper ethos of an institution, influencing how students, teachers, and administrators interact, engage, and perceive their roles. A positive school culture can promote collaboration, trust, and a shared vision, fostering environments where students thrive, teachers feel motivated, and institutional goals are effectively achieved [2]. Conversely, negative cultural elements such as mistrust, rigid hierarchies, and excessive competition can hinder educational progress and create stressful work environments for teachers [3].

Vietnamese teacher training colleges play a crucial role in preparing the next generation of educators, serving as the foundation for the nation's educational development. These institutions, particularly in the Red River Delta Region, a region known for its historical significance and rich cultural traditions-face increasing challenges. Rapid social changes, advancements in information technology, and

heightened demands for high-quality education have created new pressures for innovation and continuous improvement [4], [5]. The Vietnamese government, through landmark resolutions such as the Resolution on the fundamental and comprehensive renovation of education and training and the Resolution on building and developing Vietnamese culture to meet the requirements of sustainable development, has underscored the importance of fostering a healthy cultural environment in education [4], [5]. These policies highlight the need for teacher training colleges to cultivate environments that produce morally upright and professionally competent educators, equipped to navigate the complexities of modern education.

Research has consistently emphasized the role of school culture in determining educational outcomes. For instance, Schein's cultural model categorizes school culture into three layers: visible artifacts (symbols and rituals), espoused values (stated principles and goals), and underlying assumptions (deeply ingrained beliefs) [6]. Studies have demonstrated that positive school culture, characterized by trust, collaboration, and shared goals, is strongly correlated with improved student outcomes, higher teacher satisfaction, and enhanced institutional performance [7]. Furthermore, professional learning communities (PLCs) within schools, which thrive in cultures emphasizing collaboration and support, have been shown to improve teacher practices and student achievements [8]. Conversely, cultures dominated by competition or lack of trust can undermine the educational experience, leading to lower engagement and diminished outcomes [9], [10].

Despite these insights, the specific dynamics of school culture in Vietnamese teacher training colleges, especially in the Red River Delta, remain under-researched. While existing studies often address isolated aspects of school culture, such as communication or organizational behavior, they fall short of providing a comprehensive analysis of its overall impact on educational quality. This gap underscores the need for a deeper exploration of how cultural elements interact with institutional performance and educational outcomes in this context.

This study aims to address these gaps by investigating the relationship between school culture and educational quality in teacher training colleges in the Red River Delta Region. The research is guided by three key objectives: i) to analyze the defining characteristics of school culture in teacher training colleges, differentiating between positive and negative cultural attributes; ii) to examine the impact of school culture on educational quality indicators, including student achievement, teacher satisfaction, and research productivity; and iii) to propose actionable strategies for fostering a positive school culture, thereby contributing to the enhancement of teacher training quality in Vietnam.

The study employs a mixed-methods approach, integrating quantitative surveys and qualitative insights from interviews and observations. This methodology allows for a robust analysis of cultural dynamics and their practical implications for educational quality. By focusing on the Red River Delta—a region with a distinct cultural heritage and pivotal role in Vietnam's education system—the research offers valuable insights into the intersection of culture and education. Furthermore, the findings aim to provide practical recommendations for policymakers, institutional leaders, and educators, aligning with Vietnam's broader goals of educational reform and international integration. Through its comprehensive approach, this study seeks not only to deepen the theoretical understanding of school culture but also to contribute actionable knowledge that enhances the effectiveness of teacher training institutions. By cultivating a positive school culture, these institutions can better navigate contemporary challenges, ensuring they remain vital contributors to Vietnam's educational and societal progress.

2. METHOD

2.1. Overview of school culture and education quality

School culture may be broadly defined as a complex, interdependent system of shared values, beliefs, norms and behaviors that regulate the interactions and activities in schools. This includes all the basic things an outsider can come into contact with or observe. Low tangible such as artifacts—everything visible, audible in culture (physical environment too) language, symbols rituals ceremonies. Espoused values, what the school community says it values and believes. Basic underlying assumptions, the deeply seated automatic beliefs and implicit constructs by which members of an organization operate.

School culture: models and theories there have been many models and theories used to attempt to understand the complexities of school culture. The competing values framework defines four unique cultural types: the clan, adhocracy, hierarchy and market orientations. Different types have different values and priorities, creating a range of behavior and organizational performance. Schein proposed three levels of the construct: artifacts, espoused values and basic underlying assumptions (Schein's model for details) which allows understanding distinct layers of school culture within a system [11]. As an important dimension of school culture, the study also relies on how "school climate," or quality and character of life in schools, is perceived [12].

Qualities to be assessed in the education quality assessment. The study applies the multi-dimensional framework of measuring quality education which includes many indicators that assisted to measure how effective the teaching and learning processes were. These indicators include:

- Student achievement: reckon based on standardized test scores, graduation rates and some other academic performance indicators [13].
- School climate: measured through surveys and interviews that reflect teachers' working environments, the kind of support they receive to do their work, as well their general job satisfaction.
- Research productivity: number as well as quality of research publications, grants and other scholarly activities [14].
- Engagement: measured with learning surveys and classroom observations that chronicle how students participate in, engage with, as well as are motivated to learn [15].

The literature has indicated that school culture and educational quality have a solid relationship with an influence on each other. It has been highlighted in the literature that a positive school culture is known to play multiple roles and have numerous beneficial impacts on different variables of educational quality. A culture that is supportive and collaborative, for example, can boost teacher morale/motivation in such a way that instruction improves-so too student achievement [16]. A culture that promotes innovation and risk in teachers may also be more open to new pedagogical practices on the part of teachers, thereby or perhaps creating a less boring (and thus potentially effective) learning environment [17]. On the other end of this spectrum, a school culture where competition trumps collaboration will not provide superior education. Such a culture can result in teacher burnout, low morale and students who are disengaged. The alternatives can also potentially hinder innovation and creativity in the school, reducing the adaptability of a promising young venture to future needs/challenges [18].

A mixed-methods design was used that combined quantitative data collected through structured surveys with qualitative information from in-depth interviews and document review. This methodology allowed us to analyze trends in perceptions of school culture and why they varied as well as examine the lived experiences of faculty, students, and administrators. Incorporating these perspectives provided a more complete picture of the influence school culture has on educational quality.

2.2. Components of school culture

The components of school culture are diverse and can be categorized into several key areas. These include the school's mission and vision, the values and beliefs held by the school community, the rituals and traditions that are celebrated, and the relationships among staff, students, and parents. The mission and vision of a school provide the foundation for its culture. They articulate the school's purpose and goals, guiding decision-making and shaping the behavior of all members of the school community. Schools with a clear and compelling mission are more likely to foster a strong culture that aligns with their educational objectives.

Values and beliefs: the values and beliefs held by the school community form the core of its culture. These are often rooted in the school's history, traditions, and the broader cultural context in which it operates [8]. Schools that prioritize values such as respect, integrity, and collaboration create a positive and inclusive environment that supports student learning and well-being.

Rituals and traditions: rituals and traditions play a crucial role in reinforcing school culture. They provide opportunities for the school community to come together, celebrate achievements, and build a sense of belonging [6]. Examples include annual events, graduation ceremonies, and other school-wide activities that reinforce shared values and create a sense of continuity.

Relationships: the quality of relationships within a school is a key indicator of its culture. Positive relationships between students, teachers, and parents contribute to a supportive and collaborative environment. Schools that prioritize open communication, trust, and mutual respect are more likely to cultivate a culture that promotes academic success and social-emotional well-being [9].

Research has consistently shown that school culture has a significant impact on educational quality. A positive culture, characterized by collaboration, support, innovation, and a focus on student learning, is associated with improved student achievement, teacher satisfaction, and overall school effectiveness. In contrast, a negative culture, marked by competition, lack of trust, and a focus on compliance, can hinder student learning and create a stressful working environment for teachers.

The relationship between school culture and academic achievement is well-documented. Schools with a strong culture of learning tend to have more effective teaching practices and higher student performance [19], [20]. This is particularly evident in environments that prioritize collaboration among educators, as collaborative cultures enable teachers to share best practices and support one another in their professional development [21], [22].

Teacher satisfaction and retention: the impact of school culture extends beyond student outcomes to influence teacher retention and job satisfaction. Teachers who work in schools with a positive culture are

more likely to feel satisfied with their jobs and remain in their positions [23], [24]. This is crucial, as high teacher turnover can disrupt the continuity of instruction and negatively affect student learning outcomes.

Social-emotional well-being: school culture also significantly impacts the social and emotional well-being of students. A supportive and inclusive culture fosters a sense of belonging among students, which is essential for their overall development [25]. The concept of school connectedness, which refers to the extent to which students feel valued and supported within their school, has been linked to positive social, emotional, and academic outcomes [26].

The development of a strong school culture is essential for fostering a PLC among educators. PLCs are characterized by collaborative practices that promote continuous improvement and shared learning among teachers. Schools that prioritize professional development and create opportunities for teachers to collaborate are more likely to cultivate a culture of learning that benefits both educators and students [27].

Leadership plays a critical role in shaping school culture. Effective leaders are not only responsible for managing the day-to-day operations of the school but also for cultivating an environment that promotes shared values and collective goals [28], [29]. Research has shown that principals who actively engage with their staff and foster open communication are more likely to create a positive school culture that supports both teacher and student success [30], [31]. Transformational leadership, in particular, has been shown to enhance school culture by motivating staff and creating an environment conducive to professional growth and student success [32], [33]. Transformational leaders inspire and empower their staff to take ownership of their work, fostering a sense of shared responsibility for student outcomes.

The involvement of parents and the broader community in school activities can enhance the culture by fostering a sense of partnership and shared responsibility for student outcomes [34], [35]. Schools that engage with their communities and build strong relationships with parents are more likely to create a supportive and inclusive culture that benefits all students. The study by Hartinah [36], indicates that implementing effective multicultural education strategies in schools can significantly contribute to enhancing students' tolerance and respect for cultural diversity, thereby promoting social cohesion and unity in a diverse society [36]. In multicultural societies, schools must navigate the complexities of cultural differences and strive to create an inclusive environment that respects and values all students' backgrounds. This is particularly important in schools that serve diverse populations, as they must promote equity and social justice through their cultural practices and educational policies [37].

In the Vietnamese context, the significance of school culture in teacher training colleges has been increasingly recognized. These colleges play a crucial role in shaping the future generation of teachers, who will, in turn, influence the lives of countless students. A positive school culture in teacher training colleges can not only enhance the quality of teacher education but also instill in future teachers the values and practices necessary to create a positive learning environment for their students [38].

Teacher training colleges in Vietnam, particularly those in the Red River Delta, hold a significant place in the national education system. They are responsible for preparing future educators who will contribute to the development of the education sector. As such, the culture within these institutions is critical to ensuring that future teachers are equipped with the knowledge, skills, and values needed to succeed in the classroom.

Despite their importance, teacher training colleges in Vietnam face numerous challenges, particularly in the context of educational reform and international integration. The rapid pace of social change, advancements in technology, and increasing demands for high-quality education require these institutions to continuously improve and innovate [39]. A key factor in addressing these challenges is the development of a positive school culture that supports both staff and students in achieving their full potential.

While the significance of school culture in Vietnamese teacher training colleges is acknowledged, research in this area remains limited. Existing studies have primarily focused on specific aspects of school culture, such as communication and behavior, but have not fully explored the comprehensive impact of culture on educational quality. There is a need for more in-depth research that examines the various dimensions of school culture and their influence on the overall effectiveness of teacher training colleges.

This study examined the relationship between school culture and educational quality within Vietnamese Teacher training colleges, focusing specifically on institutions in the Red River Delta. To do this, we collected data from surveys, interviews, and document analysis involving faculty members, students, and administrators to capture their perceptions and experiences. This allowed us to analyze both the positive and negative influences of school culture on educational outcomes.

2.3. Research methods

This study uses a mixed-methods research design which includes both quantitative and qualitative data collection, as well as analysis. This balanced approach provides richer insights into the research phenomenon at greater depth since all potentials of both methods were utilized. The quantitative data give a

general picture of the representation and spread of various cultural traits, as well as their connection with indicators for educational quality. In contrast, the qualitative information provides a more in-depth understanding of the nature and expression of school culture as it is construed in practice. The research participants are lecturers, students, and administrators of some selected teacher training institutions in the Red River Delta Region Vietnam, as displayed in Table 1. The organizations surveyed were selected according to their prestige, size and balance of the teacher training colleges population in the region.

Table 1. Distribution of participants by group

Participant group	Number of participants
Administrators	40
Faculty members	150
Students	200
Total	390

This study uses three main data collection instruments:

- Surveys: the use of structured questionnaires distributed to faculty, students and administrators that contain items used to assess their perceptions of the school culture or educational quality. Surveys consist of both Likert scale closed ended questions and open-ended ones to elicit good details.
- Case studies: semi-structured interviews are conducted with purposefully selected administrators and teachers to explore their experiences as well as perceptions of school culture on educational outcomes. Interviews delve into subjects such as influences that create a school culture, obstacles and opportunities facing efforts to improve the local education context, and methods by which people work toward educational excellence.
- Analysis of documents: information is extracted from relevant documents like school policies, strategic plans or annual reports to understand the formal structures and processes that shape the organizational culture as well as educational quality.

Before the study commences, data collection approval is gained from all participating institutions and informed consent of all participants. The surveys and interviews are administered online or in person/via video interview. They are then analyzed through quantitative and qualitative methods. It is processed through statistical computer software to group them and check the relationship between variables. Descriptive and Inferential statistics are used for analyzing these data. Data analysis thematic analysis approach is used for analyzing the Input data to identify major themes and patterns in participants' narratives-qualitative artifacts. Both the result of quantitative and qualitative analysis is integrated together to provide full insight into the research phenomenon.

3. RESULTS

From here it was possible to document a far more complex cultural terrain within these teacher training colleges. Also, higher teacher satisfaction was associated with positive cultural characteristics (collaboration, support, and student-centered learning) which predicted more levels of student engagement. On the other hand, obstacles such as high levels of competition and insufficient support from the institution had negative impacts on motivation and educational quality. These findings underpin the imperative of creating a nurturing and inclusive school environment that can assist in improving opportunities for success.

3.1. Characteristics of school culture

The study revealed several key characteristics of school culture in the Red River Delta teacher training colleges. The data indicated a mixed cultural landscape, with both positive and negative elements coexisting.

3.1.1. Positive cultural traits

The positive aspects of school culture were predominantly reflected in the strong emphasis on collaboration, support, and a focus on student learning. The survey results, as shown in Table 2, illustrate these positive cultural traits. The respondents rated the importance of a “stable and practical school management” the highest (mean=2.50), indicating a strong desire for a well-organized and efficient administrative system. However, the actual manifestation of this aspect received a lower rating (mean=2.30), suggesting a gap between expectations and reality. Similarly, while the importance of “positive cooperation between lecturers, staff, employees, and students” was recognized (mean=2.47), its practical implementation was perceived to be somewhat lacking (mean=2.43). Interestingly, the aspect of “learners' behavior always

showing positivity” received the lowest importance rating (mean=2.36) but was perceived to be manifested to the highest degree (mean=2.49). This discrepancy could indicate a potential disconnect between the perceived importance of positive student behavior and the actual efforts made to cultivate it.

Table 2. Importance and level of expression of atmosphere in the school culture of pedagogical colleges

No.	Content	Level of importance (mean)	Level of expression (mean)
1	Positive cooperation between lecturers, staff, employees, and students.	2.47	2.43
2	Safe educational environment, activities are maintained and developed.	2.46	2.50
3	The management of the school is stable and practical.	2.50	2.30
4	Learners are oriented towards learning and research.	2.42	2.43
5	Learners' behavior always shows positivity.	2.36	2.49
6	Relationship with parents of learners and the community.	2.44	2.31
7	Lecturers and staff are facilitated in learning and research.	2.48	2.40

Collaboration and support: the data revealed a strong emphasis on collaborative practices and a supportive environment among faculty, staff, and students. This was evident in the high importance ratings given to “positive cooperation between lecturers, staff, employees, and students” and “lecturers and staff are facilitated in learning and research”. The interviews further corroborated this finding, highlighting instances of collaborative activities like lesson planning, peer observation, and professional development workshops.

Focus on student learning: the colleges demonstrated a clear focus on student learning and development. This was reflected in their mission statements, strategic plans, and curriculum design, which emphasized student-centered learning and holistic development. The high importance rating for “learners are oriented towards learning and research” further supports this observation, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Importance and level of expression of lecturers' cultural behavior in the school culture of pedagogical colleges

No.	Content	Level of importance (mean)	Level of expression (mean)
1	Possess good political qualities and a solid professional level.	2.84	2.51
2	Participate in and have specific scientific research projects.	3.07	2.59
3	Friendly, supportive, and help colleagues progress together.	3.36	2.28
4	Have a sense of responsibility and dedication in teaching.	2.58	3.07
5	Friendly, polite, and open in communication and pedagogical behavior.	2.53	2.82
6	Simple and honest in everyday life.	3.25	2.41
7	Humane, tolerant, close, and helpful to students.	3.38	3.35
8	Fair, able to identify and foster students' abilities.	3.18	2.51
9	Have a spirit of striving, constantly improving professional qualifications and skills.	3.15	2.44
10	Actively participate in social and charitable activities.	3.57	2.23

The strongest hope of the students was that lecturers would be “humane, tolerant, close and helpful to their students” (mean=3.38) indicating a wish for an open supportive learning environment. The actual performance of this aspect was also highly rated (mean=3.35), suggesting a good match in terms of expectation and reality for the same respect. However, the aspect of “actively participating in social and charitable activities” received the highest importance rating (mean=3.57) but was perceived to be the least manifested (mean=2.23). This significant gap highlights a potential area for improvement, suggesting that while lecturers recognize the importance of social engagement, they may face challenges or constraints in actively participating in such activities.

Again, both tables show a similar pattern that there are elements of culture that may be important but not well implemented. A targeted intervention between what schools want and the reality of their culture may be needed to bridge this gap. Thus, it signifies not just an acknowledgment of the significance of diverse cultural aspects but actual involvement in establishing and nurturing these within school culture.

These tables show that both faculty and students place high importance on collaboration, a safe and supportive environment, and a focus on student learning and development. The relatively high mean scores for these factors suggest that they are perceived as crucial components of a positive school culture. The findings from these tables provide valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of the prevailing school culture in the studied teacher training colleges. They also offer a foundation for further analysis of the impact of these cultural factors on educational quality, which will be explored in the subsequent sections.

3.1.2. Negative cultural traits

Despite the presence of positive cultural elements, the study also identified some negative cultural traits that could potentially undermine educational quality. The most notable among these was the perception of fierce competition, particularly among students.

- Fierce competition: a significant proportion of students reported feeling pressured to compete with their peers for grades and recognition. This competitive atmosphere could create a stressful and isolating learning environment, hindering collaboration and cooperation among students.
- Lack of support and focus on achievements: some participants, particularly faculty members, expressed concerns about the lack of adequate support and recognition for their efforts. This could lead to feelings of demotivation and burnout, impacting the quality of teaching and learning. Additionally, an overemphasis on achievements and test scores could create a narrow focus on academic performance at the expense of holistic student development.

The school culture in the studied teacher training colleges exhibits a blend of positive and negative characteristics. While there is a strong emphasis on collaboration, support, and student learning, the presence of fierce competition and a lack of support in certain areas could pose challenges to educational quality. These findings underscore the need for a nuanced understanding of school culture and its impact on education in the Vietnamese context.

3.2. Impact of school culture on educational quality

The research findings suggest a strong correlation between school culture and various indicators of educational quality.

- Positive impacts: positive cultural elements like collaboration, support, and a focus on learners were associated with higher levels of teacher satisfaction, student engagement, and overall school effectiveness. The data showed that teachers who felt supported and valued were more motivated and committed, leading to improved instructional practices. Similarly, a student-centered approach and a supportive environment fostered greater student engagement and satisfaction.
- Negative impacts: negative cultural aspects such as fierce competition and lack of support were found to have a detrimental effect on educational quality. The competitive atmosphere was linked to lower levels of student well-being and teacher satisfaction. Additionally, the lack of support and recognition could lead to decreased teacher motivation and hinder innovation.

3.3. Solutions for developing a positive school culture

Based on the research findings, the study proposed several solutions to foster a positive school culture in teacher training colleges:

- Fostering collaboration and support: the study recommends encouraging collaborative activities among faculty and staff, providing opportunities for professional development, and creating a supportive environment where individuals feel valued and recognized.
- Promoting student-centered learning: the study suggests shifting the focus from teacher-centered to student-centered learning approaches, encouraging active learning and critical thinking, and providing opportunities for student participation in decision-making.
- Encouraging innovation and risk-taking: the study advocates for creating a culture that values innovation and experimentation, encouraging teachers to explore new pedagogical methods and technologies.
- Addressing unhealthy competition: the study recommends promoting a healthy and supportive learning environment that values collaboration over competition, providing opportunities for students to work together, and recognizing both individual and collective achievements.
- Investing in leadership development: the study emphasizes the importance of effective leadership in shaping school culture. It recommends providing training and support for school leaders to develop their skills in creating a shared vision, promoting collaboration, and empowering teachers and students.

These solutions, if implemented effectively, can contribute to the development of a positive school culture that fosters high-quality teaching and learning in Vietnamese teacher training colleges.

4. DISCUSSION

This study aligns with the several researches [1], [6], [10]. Thus, the study established that positive school culture marked with collaboration, support to unity among teachers and learner focus can create a platform for teaching learning which in turn leads towards better educational outcomes. On the flipside, a negative school culture can be destructive to one or both of these populations and block growth and change.

However, the study also yields a number of other peculiar insights to one special angle on this issue; if from within Vietnamese teacher training colleges. The results indicate that the culture of competition,

while it can serve some students well by providing them with a drive to perform better than their peers, also leads others to feel pressured and alone. It suggests that if the preparation of teachers to ensure good learning requires realistic cooperation between teacher colleges should encourage healthy competition and cooperative education. The research emphasizes the impacts of leadership in influencing and maintaining a positive school culture. The interviews provided insight into the vital role that strong leadership plays in establishing a shared vision, fostering collaboration and enabling teachers and students with autonomy. The general spirit of the letter is that leadership development should be taken seriously and not left to chance, as good school leaders can transform a negative culture into something amazing.

In sum, this study fleshes out crucial changes in educational quality at teacher training colleges that can be attributed to differences of school cultures. We assert that this should prompt the leadership of these institutions to invest time, energy and resources in shaping a good school culture which is characterized by collaboration, support for innovation and focus on learners. In this way, they can create a more favorable context for teaching and learning that will finally result in the training of highly prepared professionals to face 21st century challenges.

5. CONCLUSION

By synthesizing a comprehensive literature review and relevant legal documents on culture with the analysis of survey data, questionnaires, and interviews conducted among administrators, faculty, and students at pedagogical universities in the Red River Delta, this study elucidates the pivotal role of positive school culture in shaping student learning outcomes. Drawing on multiple models and theories of school culture, the research examines the defining characteristics of culture within these institutions. Although participants universally recognize the foundational importance of school culture and its influence on specific academic activities, there exists a notable gap between perceived importance and actual implementation, evidenced by lower mean scores for practice versus perception. Addressing this disparity, the study proposes targeted solutions to better align members' attitudes and behaviors, thereby strengthening the overall cultural environment and enhancing the quality of teacher training.

The ongoing, fundamental reform of Vietnam's education system demands that teachers possess not only professional competence but also strong ethical character. In this context, pedagogical universities must articulate and embed core cultural values—blending Vietnam's traditional ethos of “respect for teachers” and “lifelong learning” with modern pedagogical approaches—to motivate both educators and student teachers. The findings highlight both positive cultural traits, such as collaboration, mutual support, and learner-centered practices, and negative elements, notably excessive competition that breeds stress, isolation, and diminished motivation. Positive cultural practices are correlated with higher levels of teacher satisfaction, deeper student engagement, and greater institutional effectiveness, whereas negative factors contribute to teacher burnout, low morale, and waning student motivation.

In sum, fostering a positive school culture offers a strategic pathway to elevate educational quality in teacher-training colleges across Vietnam. The study's recommendations center on promoting collaboration, support networks, and innovation—pillars essential for sustaining teacher well-being and student achievement. While the research acknowledges its limitations (single-region focus, reliance on self-reported data, and lack of longitudinal evidence), it underscores the need for future studies that span diverse regions, employ longitudinal designs, and examine external influences such as policy frameworks and societal norms. These insights carry significant implications for policymakers, educational leaders, and teacher educators committed to cultivating the next generation of high-quality instructors.

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The datasets generated and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding [PNS], author upon reasonable request.

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